

PROBLEM FACED BY LABOURS IN UNORGANIZED SECTOR: A COMPARITIVE STUDY BETWEEN DOMESTIC AND SANITATION WORKERS

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ABSTRACT

In India, more than 90% work in the informal economy, indicating work and income insecurity among more than 415 million informal sector workers. Unorganized workers face various problems and there is no platform to analyze their problems. Legislations and schemes which are created for unorganized workers are not implemented due to illiteracy and lack of awareness of the employees. Among the unorganized workers, domestic and sanitation workers are more vulnerable. The paper deals with the Problems of unorganized workers, finding out the stress level and impact on their work.

Keywords: unorganized workers, domestic and sanitation workers, stress level

I. Introduction

The employment scenario in India suggests that the share of the organised sector has been declining and most of the employment generated is in the informal sector. A large number of workers in the informal economy are actually under-employed, though they are categorised as employed. Their share in the below poverty line population is quite significant and they are unprotected by law as most of the labour laws relate to workers in the organised sector. This is essentially a micro empirical study to derive some meaningful insights. It will give a comparative results at the end of the research.

II. Who is an Unorganized Worker?

Unorganized Workers:

“The unorganized labour force is composed, without employers’ employment / social security services, of people working within unorganized companies or households excluding ordinary workers, who receive benefits under the social protection scheme.

III. Characteristics of Unorganized Sector

- a) Low scale of organization
- b) Operation of labourrelations on a casual basis, or on the basis of kinship or personal relations.

- c) Involvement of family labourers
- d) Risking of finance capital by self
- e) Free mobility within the sector
- f) Unregulated and unprotected nature
- g) Absence of fixed working hours
- h) Lack of security of employment and other social security benefits
- i) Lack of support from government
- j) Easy entry and Exit

IV Characteristics of the formal and informal sectors

Particulars	Formal sector	Informal sector
Job security	High	Low
Working hours	Fixed	Not fixed
Wages	Regulated/ Minimum wages	Not regulated/ no minimum wages
Social security including medical allowance and sick leave	Mostly provided	None or little
Labour laws including right to freedom of association and collective bargaining	Protective	No or little legal protection
Employee – employer relations with employment contract	Issue of appointment letter	Without appointment letter
Safe work environments	Safer and securer working conditions	Vulnerable to dangerous and hazardous work
Unionization	Homogeneous, highly organised and better networked	Heterogeneous, unorganized and scattered

Employment is being concentrated in the informal sectors, characterized by less remunerative and low productive work, absence of private and social security schemes, poor working conditions and lack of access to vocational training, skill development and education.

V. Problems faced by Unorganised Labours

- Job insecurity
- Low wage
- Lack of knowledge about hazardous work and occupational safety
- Paid holiday or sick leave not provided
- Ill treatment by others

VI. Sanitation Workers:

Coimbatore is second largest city and one of the most industrialized cities in Tamil Nadu which has a vast population of workers. The Coimbatore Corporation has been kept clean only because of the sanitation workers. Their work at the time of Covid -19 is never forgettable. The risk of infectious is more in the sector. There are only 5,000 sanitary workers (2520 – Permanent and 2300 – contract) where nearly 15,000 workers more could be appointed by the Coimbatore Corporation. The city comprises 100 wards.

VII. Domestic Workers:

Tamil Nadu was one of the first Indian states in which the National Domestic Workers Movement (NDWM) began. It organized domestic workers in the mid-1980s. Compared to several other Indian states, Tamil Nadu has relatively progressive legislation and programs for domestic workers, including its own Domestic Workers Welfare Board. In Tamil Nadu, There are approximately 1.8 million domestic workers.

VIII. Research Methodology

Research is defined as a study regarding a particular concern or problem using scientific methods.

IX. Objectives:

- To enlighten the problems faced by the respondents
- To find out the stress level of the respondents
- To find out the impact on their work of the respondents

X. Methods and analysis:

The data for the paper is drawn from a larger study on the status of domestic workers and sanitation workers in Coimbatore district, Tamil Nadu. A descriptive design has been made to analyze the above said objectives. 30 domestic workers who work within the household were chosen as respondents through an accidental sampling method and a structured interview schedule was designed to collect information purpose. For Selecting the sanitation workers, 95th ward was selected purposively and there were 38 respondents in the ward, Five respondents did not have a contact number and three respondents refused to answer. Hence other 30 respondents were taken by census method for the study. Total sample size for the study was 60. The collected data were analyzed with the help of SPSS statistical tool. Chi-square test was used to find out the association between variables.

Table – 1: Association between Occupation and stress level

Stress level	Occupation		Total
	Sanitation	Domestic	
Low	16	3	19
Medium	14	24	38
High	0	3	3
Total	30	30	60

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	14.526 ^a	2	.001

Significant at 1%

There is a significant association between occupation and stress level. Domestic workers are affected by more moderate level of stress than sanitation workers. The reason could be their type of work nature, low pay and with long working hours.

Table – 2: Respondent’s Satisfaction of their job

Satisfied	Occupation		Total
	Sanitation	Domestic	
Yes	30	24	54
No	0	6	6
Total	30	30	60

Majority of the respondents are satisfied with the job. Because the job does not require any mental or intellectual abilities. Hence, stress level is low and satisfied.

Table – 3: Respondent’s willingness to change their job

Want to change job	Occupation		Total
	Sanitation	Domestic	
Yes	0	6	6
No	30	24	54
Total	30	30	60

Majority of the respondents are not willing to change their job. The major reason is nearly half of the respondents (43%) belong to 35-45 age group. They don’t want to take the risk of entering into a new job.

XI. Findings

The majority of the respondents (88%) are female. Only in the sanitation sector, few were males. More than half of the respondents (60%) work for 8 hours. All the sanitation workers are contract employees. So, as per the government rules, they work for 8 hours. A majority of the respondents (72%) felt that they work for low wages. A little half of the respondents (45%)

felt a job in security. Aged workers had a feeling of job insecurity especially in the pandemic situation.

Three-fourths of the respondents (73%) have adequate holidays. Respondents can take leave whenever required with loss of pay. Half of the respondents (52%) felt ill-treated by others. Comparatively, domestic workers felt more. A few respondents in the sanitation sector stated that during COVID situations, the public respects and appreciate their work. There is a significant association between occupation and ill-treatment at 1%.

Less than half of the respondents (32%) agree that sexual exploitation exists in the sector. Comparatively, it prevails more in the domestic sector. The reason is the majority of the respondents in the sanitation sector belong to the above 45 age group. A little more than half of the respondents (55%) are covered under the social security scheme. Domestic workers are not covered, and all the sanitation workers are covered under scheme. More than half of the respondents (82%) felt that discrimination on a caste basis not prevail. All workers in the sanitation sector, from the same caste group.

The majority of the respondents (92%) don't have any health issues. And they don't have the awareness of occupational diseases in their work. Regular medical check-ups are arranged at regular intervals for sanitation workers by the government. More than half of the respondents (67%) have inadequate income to fulfil their needs. Comparatively, domestic workers have more problems. More than half of the respondents (93%) don't have any saving schemes. A little more than half of the respondents (63%) are affected by medium-level stress. The majority of the respondents (90%) are satisfied with their job.

Social Work Intervention

Social Worker can act a facilitator and emphasize government and Non- Governmental organisations to arrange free medical camp at regular intervals. Saving habits and financial management can be taught to the unorganised workers, so that their needs can be fulfilled by themselves. Many of the women employees don't know the knowledge of their salary and it is fully managed by their husbands. Education is the powerful tool which can reduce the problems among unorganised sectors. Community organisation programmes can be conducted to create awareness among the public regarding the human rights and values of unorganised workers.

XII. Conclusion

It is found that sexual exploitation, ill-treatment, and caste-based discrimination problems are more common among domestic workers than sanitation workers. Domestic workers are not covered under any social security scheme and have no savings plan. Hence, they face economic problems. In both sectors, physical health issues are not much of a problem. Domestic workers are affected more by a medium level of stress than sanitation workers. In both sectors, workers are satisfied and feel proud of their job. Only a few domestic workers wanted to change their job. Unorganized workers are happy and stay in their job due to their family situation even though they are getting low wages. They consider ill-treatment by others is a big problem.

Unorganized workers are serving society at all time. So we have to respect and treat them in a good manner at all times instead of respecting them only in crucial situations like Covid – 19.

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